

A comparative study of various imputation methods for single cell RNA sequencing data

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Abstract- Single-cell RNA-sequencing (scRNA-seq) has become an important tool to bring new insights in cellular heterogeneity, discover new cell types, and understand cell development at single-cell resolution. However, one major challenge in analyzing single cell RNA-sequencing data is the large number of false zeros called drop-outs, where genes actually expressed in a given cell are incorrectly measured as unexpressed. Therefore, the imputation of dropout values of scRNA-seq data is very much important. Several imputation methods for scRNA sequencing data have been developed in recent researches. In this paper we classify, analyze and compare the current advanced scRNA-seq data imputation methods from different perspectives. The comparison and analysis of those methods can provide suggestions for the selection of imputation methods for specific problems and diverse data and also help in downstream analysis of single cell data.

Key words: scRNA sequencing, dropout, imputation, downstream analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Bulk RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) has been the primary tool to study biological systems for many years. Traditional Bulk cell RNA sequencing data are normally used in transcriptome analysis, such as transcriptional structure, splicing patterns, genes, as well as transcriptional expression levels. Although Bulk RNA sequencing is very popular, it is unable to measure the heterogeneity inside complex tissues and cell-to-cell variability. In the recent years, advances in microfluidics and sequencing technologies have allowed us to measure the gene expression profiles of individual cells. By allowing us to monitor the biological processes at the single-cell resolution, single-cell technologies (scRNA-seq) have enabled new research directions in genomics and transcriptomics research. Advanced single-cell RNA-sequencing (scRNAseq) technologies are now emerging and enable the exploration of intra-tissue heterogeneity, stochastic gene expression, new cell-type discovery, cell differentiation and cellular lineage reconstruction at single-cell resolution.

However, scRNA-seq technology also has some challenges. One of the greatest challenges of scRNA-seq is the so-called 'drop-out' phenomenon, occurring when a gene is observed at moderate or even high expression level in one cell but is not detected in another cell. These dropouts are occurred due to inefficient messenger RNA capture or naturally due to low number of RNA transcripts and the stochastic nature of gene expression, the result is capturing only a fraction of the transcriptome of each cell and hence data that have a high degree of sparsity. The dropouts typically do not affect the highly expressed genes but may affect biologically important genes expressed at low levels such as transcription factors. It is also to be mentioned that there are many truly unexpressed genes in single cell which is called biological zeros. As a result, we get two types of zeros in the count matrix: i) Biological zeros: Genes that were not expressed at the time of sequencing and ii) Technical zeros: Genes that were expressed at the time of sequencing but not measured. Another challenge is to distinguish between these two types of zeros named technical zeros and biological zeros and impute the technical zeros.

Using scRNA-seq data, we can perform downstream analyses, such as cell clustering, differential expression analysis, identification of cell-type specific genes, marker gene selection and many others. This is particularly advantageous for studying cell-to-cell heterogeneity and cell development dynamics. These downstream analyses are all highly dependent on the accuracy of the gene expression measurements. So it, is very much important to impute the dropouts events caused by technology in the scRNA-seq data by imputation methods. However, for huge biological datasets, there is still no universal and effective imputation algorithm to eliminate batch effects and find rare cell types, and there is no clear selection strategy for the imputation method necessary for different characteristics of datasets and specific research problem. Therefore, we classify, analyze, and compare the current advanced single-cell RNA sequencing data imputation methods from different perspectives so that it can ensure the accuracy of downstream analysis.

IMPUTATION METHODS

As there are dropout values in the original gene expression matrix, many methods first pre-process and normalize the data, to eliminate the adverse effects of outliers. As there are two types of zeros in the gene expression matrix named technical zeros and biological zeros, the next step is to distinguish between these two types of zeros. Finally, these methods choose a certain strategy to impute the dropout values. There are numerous methods developed for imputation. So, classifying and comparing currently popular imputation methods is very necessary to help users provide advice when facing different datasets and different needs. In the last few years several imputation methods [20] have been developed to impute the missing values. Most of the current methods can be divided into the following four categories :

- Method based on probabilistic model
- Reconstructing the Expression value of the original gene expression matrix
- Low-rank Matrix based methods
- Method based on Deep Neural Network

Methods based on Probabilistic Model

These methods use probabilistic models to identify the technical zeros rather than true zeros, they usually only impute dropout zeros, while not involving other values that are not affected by the dropout events. In this category, we find scImpute, SAVER, BISCUIT, VIPER, bayNorm, CIDR etc. The coding links, coding language, year of publication and reference of the representative methods based on model see Table 1.

Table 1. Coding links, coding language, year of publication and reference of the representative methods based on model.

Method Name	Coding Link	Language	Year Reference
scImpute	https://github.com/Vivianstats/scImpute	R, Jupyter Notebook	2018 [10]
SAVER	https://github.com/mohuangx/SAVER	R	2018 [8]
BISCUIT	https://github.com/stevevtsa/BISCUIT	R	2016 [15]
VIPER	https://github.com/ChenMengjie/VIPER	C++, R	2018 [3]
bayNorm	https://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/bayNorm.html	R	2020 [18]
CIDR	https://github.com/VCCRI/CIDR	R, C++	2017 [11]

The scImpute [10] based on the assumption that most genes have a bimodal expression pattern that can be described by a mixture model with two components. The first component is a Gamma distribution used to account for the dropouts, whereas the second component is a Normal distribution to represent the actual gene expression levels. The expression level of gene i is considered a random variable with density function

$$f_{xi}(x) = \lambda_i \text{Gamma}(x; \alpha_i; \beta_i) + (1 - \lambda_i) \text{Normal}(x; \mu_i; \sigma_i)$$

where λ_i is the drop-out rate of gene i , α_i and β_i are shape and rate parameters of its Gamma distribution component, and μ_i and σ_i are the mean and standard deviation of its Normal distribution component. The parameters in the mixture model are estimated using Expectation-Maximization. The workflow of this method is depicted in Figure 1 and is described as follows:

- The count matrix is normalized according to the library size of each cell, and the logarithmic transformation is performed to prevent the effect of outliers.
- Cell sub-population and outliers are detected using spectral clustering.
- Dropout values were identified using a Gamma-Normal mixed model.
- Information from the same genes is borrowed from similar cells to impute in the dropout values.

Fig. 1. The workflow of scImpute method.

SAVER [8] assumes that the gene expression in the count matrix follows the Poisson-Gamma mixed distribution. The technical noise in the gene expression is approximated by the Poisson distribution, while the Gamma distribution explains the uncertainty in the real expression. The method uses the expression of other genes as the predictors, by using a Poisson Lasso regression to estimate a few prior parameters in the empirical Bayes-like approach. After the prior parameters are estimated, the SAVER outputs the posterior distribution of the true expression that quantifies the estimated uncertainty, and the posterior mean is used as the expression value for the SAVER recovery. The workflow of the method is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. The workflow of SAVER method.

Bayesian Inference for Single-cell Clustering and Imputing (BISCUIT) [15] uses the Dirichlet process mixture model to perform data normalization, cells clustering, and dropouts imputation by simultaneously inferring clustering parameters, estimating technical variations and learning co-expression structures of each cluster. The workflow of this method is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. The workflow of BISCUIT method.

VIPER [3] impute the cell where dropout is found by borrowing information from cells with similar expression pattern of the cell. This method does not perform cell clustering before imputation, and it uses a sparse non-generative regression model to actively select a sparse set of local neighborhood cells, the selection of these cells estimates their associated imputation weights in the final estimation step.

bayNorm [18] is a novel Bayesian approach for scaling and inference of scRNA-seq counts. The method’s likelihood function follows a binomial model of mRNA capture, while priors are estimated from expression values across cells using an empirical Bayes approach. For the purpose of simulating biological variability, bayNorm makes a prior analysis of the potential real gene expression level by modeling them as a variable following NB distribution. bayNorm provides an efficient, integrated solution for global scaling normalization, imputation and true count recovery of gene expression measurements from scRNA-seq data.

Clustering through Imputation and Dimensionality Reduction (CIDR)[11] is an R tool to reduce the dimensionality and clustering of single-cell RNA-seq data. The CIDR algorithm uses an ‘implicit imputation’ method to deal with dropouts. The CIDR algorithm can be divided into the following five steps: (1) Identification of dropout candidates, (2) estimation of the relationship between dropout rate and gene expression levels, (3) calculation of dissimilarity between the imputed gene expression profiles for every pair of single cells, (4) PCoA using the CIDR dissimilarity matrix, and (5) clustering using the first few principal coordinates.

Reconstructing the Expression value of the original gene expression matrix

Methods in this category typically assume that expression values from the same dataset follow a certain data structure, whereas dropout events move the values away from the underlying structure. These methods use regression techniques to infer missing values from genes or cells that have similar expression patterns. Some examples of this category are DrImpute, MAGIC, KNNImpute, PRIME, scNPF etc. The coding links, coding language, year of publication and reference of the representative methods based on reconstructing the expression value see Table 2.

Table 2. Coding links, coding language, year of publication and reference of the representative methods based on reconstructing the expression value.

Method Name	Coding Link	Language	Year Reference
DrImpute	https://github.com/gongx030/DrImpute	R, C++	2018 [7]
MAGIC	https://github.com/DppeerLab/magic	Jupyter Notebook, Python, MATLAB	2018 [5]
PRIME	https://github.com/hyundoo/PRIME	R, C++	2020 [9]
KNN-smoothing	https://github.com/yanailab/knn-smoothing	Python, R, MATLAB	2018 [19]
scNPF	https://github.com/BMILAB/scNPF	R	2019 [24]
G2S3	https://github.com/zwang-lab/g2s3	R, MATLAB	2021 [21]

DrImpute [7] computes the distance between cells using Spearman and Pearson correlations, then it performs cell clustering based on each distance matrix, followed by imputing zero values multiple times based on the resulting clusters, and finally averaging the imputation results to produce a final value for the dropouts, as shown in Figure 4. The specific workflow is as follows:

- Raw read counts are normalized by size factor and then log-transformed on the data.
- The first 5percent principal components of the similarity matrix are clustered with the k-means using the Pearson and Spearman correlations.
- Borrowing average expression values from similar cells to recover single-cell gene expression data.

Fig. 4. The workflow of DrImpute method

MAGIC [5] imputes zero values using thermal diffusion. The method first calculates the dropout gene expression values by sharing information among similar cells. Then it computes the affinity matrix between cells using a Gaussian kernel and then constructs the Markov transition matrix by normalizing and smoothing the computed affinity matrix. Finally, the method multiplies the exponentiated Markov matrix with the original data to obtain the imputed data. The workflow is as follows also shown in Figure 5:

- The input data consist of a matrix of cells by genes of the data.
- We compute a cell-by-cell distance matrix.
- The distance matrix is converted to an affinity matrix (middle) using a Gaussian kernel. A graphical depiction of the kernel function is shown in right.
- The affinities are normalized, resulting in a Markov matrix. The normalized affinities are shown for a single point as transition probabilities (right).
- To perform diffusion, we exponentiate the Markov matrix to a chosen power t .
- We multiply the exponentiated Markov matrix (left) by the original data matrix to obtain a denoised and imputed data matrix (right).

PRIME [9] (Probabilistic Imputation to reduce dropout effects in Expression profiles of single cell sequencing) is a novel imputation method that reduces dropout effects in single-cell sequencing. Here a cell correspondence network is developed and then gene expression estimates based on transcriptome profiles for the local sub-network of cells of the same type are adjusted. The workflow of this method is shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. The workflow of PRIME method.

k-nearest neighbor smoothing (kNN-smoothing) [19] algorithm is designed to reduce noise by aggregating information from similar cells in a computationally efficient and statistically tractable manner. The algorithm is based on the observation that across protocols, the technical noise exhibited by UMI- filtered scRNA-Seq data closely follows Poisson statistics. Smoothing is performed by first identifying the nearest neighbors of each cell in a step-wise fashion, based on partially smoothed and variance-stabilized expression profiles, and then aggregating their transcript counts.

scNPF [24] is an integrative scRNA-seq preprocessing framework assisted by network propagation and network fusion, for recovering gene expression loss, correcting gene expression measurements, and learning similarities between cells. scNPF leverages the context-specific topology inherent in the given data and the priori knowledge derived from publicly available molecular gene-gene interaction networks to augment gene-gene relationships in a data driven manner.

G2S3 [21] is a gene graph-based imputation method for single-cell RNA sequencing data. The method imputes dropouts by borrowing information from adjacent genes in a sparse gene graph learned from gene expression profiles

across cells. G2S3 is used for recovering gene expression, restoring cell subtype separation, reconstructing cell trajectories, identifying differentially expressed genes, and restoring gene regulatory and correlation relationships.

Low-rank Matrix based method

This type of method based on the low rank matrix that identifies the potential spatial representation of the cell by capturing the linear relationship among them, and then reconstructs the gene expression matrix from the low rank which is no longer sparse. McImpute, scRMD, ALRA, PBLR, CMF-Impute are some examples of this type of method. The coding links, coding language, year of publication and reference of the representative methods based on Low-rank matrix see Table 3.

Table 3. Coding links, coding language, year of publication and reference of the representative methods based on Low-rank matrix.

Method Name	Coding Link	Language	Year Reference
McImpute	https://github.com/aanchalMongia/McImpute_scRNAseq	MATLAB	2019 [13]
scRMD	https://github.com/XiDsLab/scRMD	R	2020 [2]
ALRA	https://github.com/KlugerLab/ALRA	R	2018 [12]
PBLR	https://github.com/amsszlh/PBLR	MATLAB,R, Fortran,C	2018 [25]
CMF-Impute	https://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/SC3.html	R	2020 [23]
ZIFA	https://github.com/epierson9/ZIFA	Python	2015 [14]

McImpute [13] models the gene expression matrix as a low-rank matrix, takes the normalized gene expression matrix as the input of the Nuclear-norm minimization algorithm, and recovers the gene expression value of the complete matrix by solving non-convex optimization problems. An important feature of McImpute is that it does not assume that gene expression follows a certain distribution. We give a simple framework as shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. The workflow of McImpute method.

scRMD [2] imputes the dropout values in the gene expression matrix by robust matrix decomposition. It decomposes the observed gene expression matrix into three contents: potential gene expression matrix, dropouts, and noise, and transforms the dropout value imputation problem into an optimization problem. The optimal gene expression value affected by dropout events is estimated by the alternating direction multiplier method. We give a simple framework as shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. The workflow of scRMD method.

Adaptively thresholded Low-Rank Approximation (ALRA) [12] is a method for imputation of scRNA-seq data. ALRA takes advantage of the non-negativity and low-rank structure of an expression matrix to selectively impute technical zeros. The first step of ALRA is to compute a low-rank approximation of the observed matrix using the singular vector decomposition. The rank k of the approximation is automatically determined by a simple procedure described in the Online Methods. The matrix resulting from this low-rank approximation, in general, has no zeros. Hence, the last step of ALRA is to restore the biological zeros in the matrix by thresholding its entries. We give a simple framework as shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. The workflow of ALRA method.

PBLR is a cell sub-population based bounded low-rank (PBLR) [25] method to impute the dropouts of scRNA-seq data. PBLR first extracts a set of highly variably expressed genes. In the next step PBLR builds a consensus matrix by employing either symmetric non-negative matrix factorization and incomplete NMF on several affinity matrices or Leiden algorithm on shared nearest neighbor graph with various resolution values. This inferred consensus matrix is further used as the input of hierarchical clustering to determine final cell sub-populations and sub-matrices.

Collaborative Matrix Factorization-based method (CMF-Impute) [23] is novel method for scRNA-seq data imputation, which simultaneously takes into account for the cell and gene similarity. CMF-Impute aims to find two feature matrices whose products provide the best approximation to the original matrix.

Method based on Deep Neural Network

These type of method methods rely on deep neural networks to denoise the data and to impute the missing values. Method in this category include AutoImpute, DCA, DeepImpute, scScope etc. The coding links, coding language, year of publication and reference of the representative methods based on deep neural network see Table 4.

Table 4. Coding links, coding language, year of publication and reference of the representative methods based on deep neural network.

Method Name	Coding Link	Language	Year Reference
AutoImpute	https://github.com/divyanshu-	Python, R	2018 [17]

	talwar/AutoImpute		
DCA	https://github.com/theislab/dca	Python	2019 [6]
DeepImpute	https://github.com/lanagarmire/DeepImpute	Python, Dockerfile	Makefile, 2019 [1]
scScope	https://github.com/AltschulerWu-Lab/scScope	Python	2019 [4]
GNNImpute	https://github.com/Lav-i/GNNImpute	Python, Dockerfile	2021 [22]
GraphSCI	https://github.com/epierson9/ZIFA	Jupyter Python	Notebook, 2021 [16]

AutoImpute [17] is a novel method for sparse gene expression matrix imputation using overcomplete autoencoders. AutoImpute learns the inherent distribution of the input scRNA-seq data and imputes the missing values accordingly with minimal modification to the biologically silent gene expression values. Here, the aim is to use overcomplete autoencoders to capture the distribution of the given sparse gene expression data and hence, regenerate a complete version of the same. This is done by feeding the sparse gene expression. The workflow is shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. The workflow of AutoImpute method

DCA [6] is an imputation method based on automatic encoder. Here a deep count autoencoder network (DCA) is used to denoise scRNA-seq datasets. DCA takes the count distribution, overdispersion and sparsity of the data into account using a negative binomial noise model with or without zero inflation, and nonlinear gene-gene dependencies are captured. The workflow is shown in Figure 11.

Fig. 11. The workflow of DCA method.

DeepImpute [1] is a deep neural network-based imputation algorithm that uses dropout layers and loss functions to learn patterns in the data, allowing for accurate imputation. DeepImpute is a deep neural network model that imputes genes in a divide-and-conquer approach, by constructing multiple sub-neural networks. Doing so offers the advantage of reducing the complexity by learning smaller problems and fine-tuning the sub-neural networks. The framework is shown in Figure 12.

Fig. 12. The workflow of DeepImpute method

scScope [4] is a deep-learning based imputation method. scScope utilizes a recurrent network layer to iteratively perform imputations on zero-valued entries of input scRNA-seq data. scScope’s architecture allows imputed output to be iteratively improved through a selected number of recurrent steps.

GNNImpute [22] is a deep learning method based on a graph attention neural network. It introduces the attention mechanism that can assign weights to different similar cells according to attention coefficients. It can establish nonlinear relationships between genes by learning low-dimensional embedding of expressions through the autoencoder structure network. This method can learn the gene co-expression patterns of similar cells by aggregating information from multi-level neighbors. The co-expression patterns can help recover low-expressed genes. GNNImpute reduces the dropout noise and improves the gene expression profile of cells.

DIFFERENT APPROACHES OF CLASSIFICATIONS OF THE VARIOUS IMPUTATION METHODS

We have discussed so far the existing imputation methods by classifying them into four categories. But the classification can be done in different ways also. Existing scRNA-seq imputation methods can also be categorized into two main approaches as follows;

- Method which only impute dropouts: These methods impute the only dropouts in gene expression matrix. Some examples of this type of methods are scImpute, drImpute, LSImpute etc.

- Methods alter all gene expressions: Method in this category alter all gene expression values including high non-zero values. Some examples of this type of methods are MAGIC, SAVER, DCA etc.

The third classification angle divides existing imputation methods into two categories named

- Model based methods: Methods in the first category model the data using a mixture of two different distributions: one distribution represents the actual gene expression while the other accounts for the dropout events. Next, they estimate the model parameters and true expression values using the Expectation-Maximization algorithm. Methods in this category include scImpute, SAVER, BISCUIT etc.

- Model free methods: Methods in the second category assume that gene expression values follow a certain data structure, whereas dropout events move the values away from this data structure. These methods use regression techniques to impute missing values from genes or cells that have similar expression patterns. Methods in this category include MAGIC, DrImpute, scScope, DCA, DeepImpute etc.

The fourth way, the imputation methods can be categorized into Statistical methods or Machine Learning based methods according to how the imputation information is used from the observed data.

- Statistical methods: These methods also include mean/mode completer, expectation maximization imputation, regression imputation etc. Some example of this type of methods are scImpute, SAVER, CIDR, scRMD, scNPF, CMF-IMpute etc.

- Machine learning based methods: These methods use machine learning for imputation like clustering imputation. Some examples are BISCUIT, LSImpute, PRIME, DrImpute, AutoImpute, McImpute, SAVER-X, GraphSCI, GNNImpute etc.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

We have reviewed various existing imputation methods developed for imputing missing values named dropouts. We have also categorized and analyzed the various imputation methods on different approaches. In the imputation function, it may not be possible to distinguish between biological zeros and technical zeros, usually only technical zeros are considered in most of the imputation methods. Method based on probabilistic model produces fewer false positives, but it depends on the homogeneity or heterogeneity of the dataset. Method based on reconstructing the expression value helps to reduce noise, but it may produce many false positives. It is observed that the datasets with small effect size genes, the first kind of method may be better than the second kind of algorithm. Method based on low-rank matrix, and the method based on deep learning neural network are based on data reconstruction. The method based on low-rank matrix captures the linear relationship, while the deep learning method deals with the nonlinear relationship.

After analyzing of various imputation methods, we have found that PRIMRE, CIDR, MISC etc provide the best performance in terms of computing time. When we consider memory consumption, SCC, G2S3 etc provide the highest memory efficiency. When we consider scalability as parameter, AutoImpute, scImpute, TRANSLATE, MAGIC, kNN-smoothing etc. demonstrate high scalability. Based on a comprehensive comparison of time, memory, and scalability, ENHANCE, MAGIC, SAVER, SAVER-X provide very good overall performance.

It is to be noted that the best imputation method depends on genes and datasets. In other words, there is no single best way to perform. For example, a network-based approach may perform well in cell types that meet the co-expression model assumptions, while it may fail for the same gene in other cell types that do not meet these assumptions. Therefore, the best imputation method depends not only on genes but on datasets also. We should no longer look for a single best imputation method for single cell RNA sequencing data. So, we have to find the best way for a specific combination of genes and experimental conditions for finding best suitable imputation method for a particular scRNA sequencing dataset.

REFERENCES:

1. Cédric Arisdakessian, Olivier Poirion, Breck Yunits, Xun Zhu, and Lana X. Garmire. Deepimpute: an accurate, fast, and scalable deep neural network method to impute single-cell rna-seq data. *Genome Biology*, 20(1):211, Oct 2019.
2. Chong Chen, Changjing Wu, Linjie Wu, Xiaochen Wang, Minghua Deng, and Ruibin Xi. scRMD: imputation for single cell RNA-seq data via robust matrix decomposition. *Bioinformatics*, 36(10):3156–3161, 03 2020.
3. Mengjie Chen and Xiang Zhou. Viper: variability-preserving imputation for accurate gene expression recovery in single-cell rna sequencing studies. *Genome Biology*, 19(1):196, Nov 2018.
4. Yue Deng, Feng Bao, Qionghai Dai, Lani F Wu, and Steven J Altschuler. Scalable analysis of cell-

- type composition from single-cell transcriptomics using deep recurrent learning. *Nat Methods*, 16(4):311–314, March 2019.
5. David Dijk, Roshan Sharma, Juozas Nainys, et al. Recovering gene interactions from single-cell data using data diffusion. *Cell*, 174, 06 2018.
 6. Gökçen Eraslan, Lukas M. Simon, Maria Mircea, Nikola S. Mueller, and Fabian J. Theis. Single-cell rna-seq denoising using a deep count autoencoder. *Nature Communications*, 10(1):390, Jan 2019.
 7. Wuming Gong, Il-Youp Kwak, Pruthvi Pota, et al. Drimpute: imputing dropout events in single cell rna sequencing data. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 19(1):220, Jun 2018.
 8. Mo Huang, Jingshu Wang, Eduardo Torre, Hannah Dueck, Sydney Shaffer, Roberto Bonasio, John I. Murray, Arjun Raj, Mingyao Li, and Nancy R. Zhang. Saver: gene expression recovery for single-cell rna sequencing. *Nature Methods*, 15(7):539–542, Jul 2018.
 9. Hyundoo Jeong and Zhandong Liu. PRIME: a probabilistic imputation method to reduce dropout effects in single-cell RNA sequencing. *Bioinformatics*, 36(13):4021–4029, 04 2020.
 10. Wei Vivian Li and Jingyi Jessica Li. An accurate and robust imputation method scimpute for single-cell rna-seq data. *Nature Communications*, 9(1):997, Mar 2018
 11. Peijie Lin, Michael Troup, and Joshua W. K. Ho. Cidr: Ultrafast and accurate clustering through imputation for single-cell rna-seq data. *Genome Biology*, 18(1):59, Mar 2017.
 12. George C. Linderman, Jun Zhao, Manolis Roulis, Piotr Bielecki, Richard A. Flavell, Boaz Nadler, and Yuval Kluger. Zero-preserving imputation of single-cell rna-seq data. *Nature Communications*, 13(1):192, Jan 2022.
 13. Aanchal Mongia, Debarka Sengupta, and Angshul Majumdar. McImpute: Matrix completion based imputation for single cell RNA-seq data. *Front Genet*, 10:9, January 2019.
 14. Emma Pierson and Christopher Yau. Zifa: Dimensionality reduction for zero-inflated single-cell gene expression analysis. *Genome Biology*, 16(1):241, Nov 2015.
 15. Sandhya Prabhakaran, Mélanie Rey, Osvaldo Zagordi, et al. Hiv haplotype inference using a propagating dirichlet process mixture model. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Computational Biology and Bioinformatics*, 11(1):182–191, 2013.
 16. Jiahua Rao, Xiang Zhou, Yutong Lu, Huiying Zhao, and Yuedong Yang. Imputing single-cell rna-seq data by combining graph convolution and autoencoder neural networks. *iScience*, 24(5):102393, 2021.
 17. Divyanshu Talwar, Aanchal Mongia, Debarka Sengupta, and Angshul Majumdar. Autoimpute: Autoencoder based imputation of single-cell rna-seq data. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1):16329, Nov 2018.
 18. Wenhao Tang, Francois Bertaux, Philipp Thomas, Claire Stefanelli, Malika Saint, Samuel Marguerat, and Vahid Shahrezaei. bayNorm: Bayesian gene expression recovery, imputation and normalization for single-cell RNA-sequencing data. *Bioinformatics*, 36(4):1174–1181, 10 2019.
 19. Florian Wagner, Yun Yan, and Itai Yanai. K-nearest neighbor smoothing for high-throughput single-cell rna-seq data. *bioRxiv*, 2018.
 20. Mengyuan Wang, Jiatao Gan, Changfeng Han, Yanbing Guo, Kaihao Chen, Ya-zhou Shi, and Ben-gong Zhang. Imputation methods for scrna sequencing data. *Applied Sciences*, 12(20), 2022.
 21. Weimiao Wu, Yunqing Liu, Qile Dai, Xiting Yan, and Zuoheng Wang. G2S3: A gene graph-based imputation method for single-cell RNA sequencing data. *PLoS Comput Biol*, 17(5):e1009029, May 2021.
 22. Chenyang Xu, Lei Cai, and Jingyang Gao. An efficient scrna-seq dropout imputation method using graph attention network. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 22(1):582, Dec 2021.
 23. Junlin Xu, Lijun Cai, Bo Liao, Wen Zhu, and JiaLiang Yang. CMF-Impute: an accurate imputation tool for single-cell RNA-seq data. *Bioinformatics*, 36(10):3139–3147, 02 2020.
 24. Wenbin Ye, Guoli Ji, Pengchao Ye, Yuqi Long, Xuesong Xiao, Shuchao Li, Yaru Su, and Xiaohui Wu. scnpf: an integrative framework assisted by network propagation and network fusion for preprocessing of single-cell rna-seq data. *BMC Genomics*, 20(1):347, May 2019.
 25. Lihua Zhang and Shihua Zhang. Imputing single-cell RNA-seq data by considering cell heterogeneity and prior expression of dropouts. *Journal of Molecular Cell Biology*, 13(1):29–40, 10 2020.